

D7.2 Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan

Project title: BEYOND BAD APPLES: Towards a Behavioral and Evidence-Based Approach to Promote Research Ethics and Research Integrity in Europe

Project acronym: BEYOND

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Deliverable Factsheet

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BEYOND Consortium

	ROLE	NAME	Acronym	Country
1.	Coordinator	University of Oslo	UiO	Norway
2.	Partner	European Network of Research Ethics Committees	EUREC	Germany
3.	Partner	French Office for Research Integrity	OFIS	France
4.	Partner	French Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and the Environment	INRAE	France
5.	Partner	Oslo Metropolitan University	OsloMet	Norway
6.	Partner	Finnish National Board on Research Integrity TENK	TENK	Finland
7.	Partner	University of Central Lancashire-Cyprus	UCLanCY	Cyprus
8.	Partner	University of Helsinki	UH	Finland
9.	Partner	University of Humanistic Studies	UHS	The Netherlands
10.	Partner	University of Latvia	UL	Latvia
11.	Partner	University of Tartu	UTARTU	Estonia
12.	Partner	Stichting VUMC / The Embassy of Good Science	VUMC	The Netherlands
13.	AP	Trilateral Research LTD	TRI	UK
14.	AP	Heriot-Watt University	HWU	SCT

Abbreviations

DEC: Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication; FFP: Falsification, Fabrication, & Plagiarism; HEI: Higher Education Institution; QRP: Questionable Research Practices; RDI: Research, Development and Innovation; RE/RI: Research Ethics and Research Integrity; RFO: Research Funding Organisation; R&I: Research and Innovation; RM: Research Misconduct; RPO: Research Performing Organisation (both research organisations and higher education institutions)

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1. Introduction

BEYOND is a multistakeholder, EU-funded consortium, which includes universities and research integrity offices and other organizations from multiple EU-member nations and the United Kingdom. The BEYOND consortium is led by the University of Oslo. Consortium partners are the European Network of Research Ethics Committees (EUREC), the French Office for Research Integrity (OFIS), the French Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and the Environment (INRAE),

Heriot-Watt University, Oslo Metropolitan University, the Finnish National Board on Research Integrity TENK, Trilateral Research, University of Central Lancashire-Cyprus (UCLanCY), University of Helsinki, University of Humanistic Studies in the Netherlands, University of Latvia, University of Tartu (Fig.1).

BEYOND explores and advances individual and institutional responsibilities in the promotion of research ethics (RE) and research integrity (RI), with particular focus on the prevention of research misconduct (RM) through guidance and educational instruments.

Fig 1. Project partners in BEYOND

The project contributes to ensuring that the work carried out in the EU to tackle research misconduct relies on evidence-based foundations, moving beyond simplistic notions such as the 'bad apples' framework (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Main goals of BEYOND as illustrated on BEYOND's project page (<https://beyondbadapples.eu/project/>). The icons above have been developed in connection with our website. They are used to bring a uniform look for publications of the project.

1.1 Objectives of BEYOND

The main goal of the BEYOND project is to robustly explore and advance individual and institutional responsibilities in RM and in the promotion of RE/RI. The consortium will achieve this goal by developing co-created, needs and case-based, streamlined, and best practices-based measures meant to engage, guide, and equip stakeholders in research through guidance and educational instruments.

To achieve this goal, BEYOND will target the following specific objectives (SO) based on four key building blocks: EXPLORE, ENGAGE, GUIDE and EQUIP (Table 1).

Table 1. BEYOND Specific Objectives (SO)

SO1: EXPLORE	Identification of behavioral knowledge and needs through a state-of-the-art review of personal and institutional responsibilities on RE/RI
Measures and outcomes	Insights from literature review on behavioral ethics and moral psychology and review of real-life cases of RM (M12)
SO2: EXPLORE & ENGAGE	Facilitation of bottom-up and solution-oriented public consultations on RE/RI needs, knowledge, and perspectives on the efficacy of RE/RI interventions
Measures and outcomes	Insights from Stakeholder Advisory Board (M6) Public consultation of at least 200 stakeholders and a report of the results (M21)
SO3: EXPLORE & GUIDE	Design and testing of psychologically informed interventions as methodologies to promote RE/RI and address RM from the perspective of personal and institutional responsibilities
Measures and outcomes	Report on tackling problematic research practices through contextual interventions (M24)
SO4: EXPLORE & GUIDE	Developing methodologies to measure the short-, medium-, and long-term impact of RE/RI trainings on attitudes and behaviors of students and researchers
Measures and outcomes	Report on explored methodologies and measurements and large-scale measurement instruments on short-, medium-, and long-term training effects (M24)
SO5: EQUIP & GUIDE	Providing guidance through a best-practice manual, guidelines that supplement standard operating procedures, and a 2030 roadmap towards improving RE/RI culture
Measures and outcomes	Best-practices manual to address RM and promote RE/RI; Guidelines to facilitate the adoption of case-based methodologies; 2030 RE/RI Roadmap (M36)
SO6: EQUIP & ENGAGE	Fostering the broad uptake of project outputs through strategic synergy and the provision of training materials that supplement existing RE/RI training materials
Measures and outcomes	Pilot-tested training materials; horizontal coordination with other EU projects; accomplished Dissemination and Communication measures (M36)

Table 2 (here below) lists the deliverables and milestones of the project.

Table 2. Deliverables and Milestones of BEYOND

Year 2023		
Month	Deliverable	Milestone
M3	D7.1 Plan for Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication of Results	
M5		M7.2 Communications activity launch
M6	D2.1 Consultation plan to engage the public and expert stakeholders D8.1 Data Management Plan D8.2 Ethics Management Plan	M1.1 Completion of the literature review M2.1 List of stakeholders and recruitment plan M7.1 BEYOND branding and logo M8.1 Stakeholder Advisory Board established
M8	D1.1 Policy Brief: Addressing socioeconomic consequences of RM	
M9		M2.2 Functioning electronic platform for public consultation
M10	D6.1 Strategy for the development of supplementary trainer guide and new training materials and tools	M7.3 Cross-SwafS workshop 1 in ENRIO Congress 2023, Paris

M12	<p>D1.2 Insights from the literature review and review of cases</p> <p>D7.2 Updated Plan for Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication of Results</p> <p>D7.3 Policy Briefing 1</p>	<p>M3.1 Model of selective reporting behaviors and a systematic overview of potential nudging interventions for change</p> <p>M8.2 Stakeholder advisory board coordination</p>
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Year 2024		
Month	Deliverable	Milestone
M14		M4.1 Identification and implementation of selected measurement methods
M18	D1.3 Systematic review of RM validated instruments	
M20		<p>M2.3 Workshop for analysis of preliminary results of public consultation</p> <p>M4.2 Designing principles for large-scale feasible measurement in a short, medium, and long-term perspective</p>
M21	D2.2 Report on the results of the BEYOND public consultation	

M22	D6.2 Report on supplementary trainer guide and new training materials on RE/RI	
M23	D4.1 Report on the methodologies and measurements explored, and guidelines including functionality, feasibility and reliability of each method for the assessment of training initiatives and interventions in RI	
M24	D3.1 Report on contextually sensitive framework for defining QRPs, including nudges D3.2 Report on tackling QRPs through contextual interventions D4.2 Large-scale feasible	
	measurement instruments on short, medium and long-term training effects adapted to the needs of a variety of target groups and different fields/domains	
Year 2025		
Month	Deliverable	Milestone
M25		M6.1 Training materials and tools available on Embassy of Good Science and integrated into ENERI Classroom

M34	D6.3 Report on pilot-tests of training materials and tools	
M35	D5.1 Guidelines D5.2 Best practice manual D5.3 2030 Roadmap	
M36	D7.4 Policy Briefing 2	M6.2 Final version of training materials and tools available on Embassy of Good Science and integrated into ENERI Classroom

2. Stakeholders

The five key stakeholder groups BEYOND works with are 1) the research community, 2) RPOs and RFOs, 3) policymakers, 4) RE/RI committees and officers, and 5) the general public. The stakeholder recruitment plan (M2.1) and the establishment of the Stakeholder Advisory Board (M8.1) guide the discussion with stakeholders and help determine the best channels and methods of communication with stakeholders.

The activities of BEYOND are targeted at the research ecosystem, as all stakeholders in this system benefit from an improved RE/RI culture. This ecosystem includes actors and organisations in a position to implement policies, guidelines and training materials: RPOs, RFOs, HEIs, research ethics committees, research integrity offices and officers, educators, and research publishers.

Through horizontal coordination and the involvement of The Embassy of Good Science, acting as a central community hub for RE/RI projects and initiatives, BEYOND liaises with other relevant EC funded projects for purposes of co-learning, efficient dissemination and exploitation activities and good use of project resources in all projects.

Engagement with trainees and research participants is part of the intervention and measurement activities in WP3 and WP4. This participation is also an opportunity for project partners to communicate about and disseminate the message from BEYOND.

Thanks to the inclusion of the general public, civil society organisations, and NGOs within the project's stakeholder groups BEYOND contributes to strengthen social trust in science and participates in the public discourse on research integrity.

2.2 Stakeholder Advisory Board

The goal of BEYOND is to strengthen adherence to research ethics and integrity standards, and cultivate a research culture that prioritizes ethical practices. Achieving this goal requires insight, expertise and advice from a wide range of stakeholders. To this end, BEYOND has established a Stakeholder Advisory Board (SAB). The board provides expertise, guidance, and strategic input based on the members' specialized knowledge and experience and will support the project partners in the development of high-quality output and wide dissemination.

The Stakeholder Advisory Board links the BEYOND consortium to the European Federation of Academies of Sciences and Humanities, ALLEA (the curator of the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity), ENRIO, EARMA, UNESCO (specifically the Bureau of the Intergovernmental Bioethics Committee), the European Network for Academic Integrity, EU-funded projects (e.g. Path2Integrity, Trust), and other European and international public and private institutions and stakeholder groups.

The members of the SAB provide external expertise to BEYOND throughout the duration of the project in the development of high-quality outputs that explore and promote individual and institutional responsibilities in the prevention of research misconduct and the promotion of research ethics and research integrity. To this end, all SAB members will be informed and consulted about project activities and outputs in the bi-annual Stakeholder Advisory Board meetings.

In addition to being informed and providing general feedback, the SAB members are free to choose between different opportunities for active involvement in project activities related to the development, analysis, validation or dissemination of project outputs. SAB members are invited to participate actively in consultations, focus groups, co-creation workshops and in the development and validation of training materials and RE/RI guidelines. Depending on their expertise, SAB members can also play a key role in generating outputs and in the advancement of the project.

The level of engagement is flexible, allowing SAB members to choose their degree of involvement based on their interests and availability. As a minimum requirement, board members are expected to attend the biannual meetings throughout the three-year project duration. SAB members can choose to change their level of engagement at any time.

Four different levels of engagement have been identified:

- Inform - SAB members will be kept informed of project activities and outcomes through SAB meetings (twice a year) and a newsletter (four times a year). Beyond will seek advice and feedback from SAB members based on their expertise and experience.
- Consult - SAB members are invited to participate in short consultations (opinions and suggestions on specific tasks).
- Involve - SAB members will be invited to take part in the development of methodologies, interviews, surveys.
- Collaborate - SAB members are invited to play an active role in the decision-making process and in the full development of the project outputs (e.g. policy briefs, publications, deliverables, etc.).

SAB members are free to choose in which of these clusters they would like to be involved as advisors. A live shared document is created to allow all SAB members to provide and change their preferences.

The five clusters are the following:

- Cluster 1: evidence on the causes and consequences of research misconduct as well as institutional and individual needs in the realm of research misconduct prevention;
- Cluster 2: psychologically informed interventions for ethical behaviour to promote research integrity on the individual and institutional levels;
- Cluster 3: methodologies to measure the impact of research ethics and integrity training on attitudes and behaviours of students and researchers;
- Cluster 4: training materials and tools that supplement existing research ethics and integrity trainings;
- Cluster 5: best practice manual and guidelines for preventing research misconduct and promoting research ethics and integrity.

3. Communication, dissemination and exploitation activities

The communication, dissemination and exploitation activities and channels for BEYOND are determined based on the project deliverables and milestones and the needs of stakeholder groups. The goal of all communication and dissemination work is to enhance the exploitability of project results.

Communication activities provide information about the project to specialist stakeholders and a wider general (non-specialist) audience throughout the project.

Dissemination activities make project results public to stakeholders and policymakers in order to maximise the impact of the project, widening the scope of exploitation by new stakeholder groups and potential end-users of the project deliverables.

Exploitation activities (focused towards the end stage of the project) make efficient use of project results for knowledge transfer in policymaking and by stakeholders.

Key dissemination and exploitation channels:

- Trainings where project materials and outcomes are adopted and implemented
- Academic conferences and mutual learning exercises organised by stakeholders
- High-quality academic journals
- Network meetings, e.g. NERQ Network, WCRI, ENRIO congresses
- The Embassy of Good Science
- The project's public consultation

The project website and social media channels are used to amplify these dissemination and exploitation activities.

The success of the project can be measured particularly with the following:

- The adoption and implementation of training materials, measured by e.g. the Embassy of Good Science repository usage
- Number of views and citations of project's publications
- Uptake of the results of the project by RE/RI existing or upcoming policies and codes of conduct
- Uptake of project's results in local or national training programs

Table 3 (here below) lists the deliverables and milestones most relevant for dissemination.

Table 3. Deliverables and milestones relevant to dissemination

No	Deliverable / Milestone	WP	Lead	Delivery date
M7.2	Communications activity launch: BEYOND website	WP7	TENK	M5
M7.3	Horizontal Coordination: Cross-SwafS workshop 1	WP7	Ofis	M9
D6.1	Strategy for the development of supplementary trainer guide and new training materials and tools	WP6	EUREC	M10
D1.2	Insights from the literature review and review of cases	WP1	TRI	M12
D7.3	Policy brief: Addressing socio-economic consequences of RM	WP7	TRI	M12
D1.3	Systematic review of RM validated instruments	WP1	UiO	M18
D2.2	Report on the public consultation results	WP2	UL	M21
D6.2	Report on supplementary trainer guide and new training materials on RE/RI	WP6	EUREC	M22
D4.1	Report on measurements and guidelines for the assessment of training initiatives and interventions in RI	WP4	UH	M23
D3.1	Report on contextually sensitive framework for defining QRPs	WP3	UT	M24
D3.2	Report on tackling QRPs through contextual interventions	WP3	UT	M24
D4.2	Measurement of short, medium and longterm training effects for various target groups	WP4	UH	M24
D6.3	Report on pilot-tests of training materials and tools	WP6	EUREC	M34
D5.1	Guidelines	WP5	UiO	M35
D5.2	Best practice manual	WP5	UiO	M35
D5.3	2030 Roadmap	WP5	UiO	M35

3.1 Communication

Communication activities are targeted towards all stakeholders to ensure the effective dissemination and exploitation of project outcomes throughout the lifespan of BEYOND.

The aims of communication activities are:

- To inform and involve the general public in an accessible and inviting ways about the project's aims and activities;

To raise awareness among stakeholder groups about the objectives, activities and results of BEYOND.

4. Dissemination and communication channels and tools

The main communication channels are: the project website and social media channels, The Embassy of Good Science, the public consultation, networking activities with other EU projects, scientific publications and presentations at conferences.

4.1 Project website and social media

The project website <https://beyondbadapples.eu/> was published in May 2023 by WP7 (M7.2). (Fig. The website and visual elements of the project were created by the Finnish design company Taikalehto. The website is maintained by the Finnish National Board on Research Integrity (TENK) and is hosted on the secure servers of the Federation of Finnish Learned Societies in Finland.

The website contains an inviting project description, introductions of project members and SAB members and other information about ongoing activities, e.g. project surveys for the public consultation (M2.2). The website will be maintained only for the duration of the project. In order to ensure the availability of results after the end of the project all the projects outputs will also be presented on the Embassy of Good Science.

Matomo Analytics is used to collect websites analytics. Matomo Analytics is an open-source web analytics platform that allows users to retain complete ownership of the data.

Fig. 3. Screenshot of the landing page of www.beyondbadapples.eu

Besides the project website, BEYOND is also active on social media. Project news, activities and results are disseminated via LinkedIn (BEYOND BAD APPLES, 48 followers on 20th Dec 2023).

4.2 The Embassy of Good Science and Zenodo

BEYOND will create sustainable participation and dissemination of projects results via Embassy of Good Science and Zenodo (zenodo.org). Outcomes of the project will be presented on the dedicated BEYOND project page and various sections of the platform, for example the training section of the Embassy of Good Science, where a dedicated page will be created for training materials.

A project page has already been created and is available on the [community section](#) of The Embassy (Fig. 4). This page includes news, events and a repository for the project results. The repository is for now only available to project members and will be made public once the deliverables are approved and made public.

OMMISSION

Fig. 4. BEYOND project page on The Embassy of Good Science available at <https://community.embassy.science/categories>

Output that will be made available on the Embassy of Good Science include:

- Training guides and new training materials
- Report on the measurements and guidelines for the assessment of training initiatives and interventions in RI (D4.1)
- Measurement of short, medium and long-term training effects for various target groups (D 4.2)
- Strategy for the development of supplementary trainer guide and new training materials and tools (D6.1)
- Report on supplementary trainer guide and new training materials on RE/RI (D6.2)
- Report on pilot-tests of training materials and tools (D 6.3)
- Guidelines (D5.1), Best practice manual (D5.2) and 2023 Roadmap (D5.3)

The Wiki nature of the platform allows trainers and users to reuse the materials according to their needs and to create their own trainings by adapting and combining the resources created by BEYOND and other resources available on the platform, thereby fostering cross-pollination between results of various projects and integration of the new material into a broader collection of training resources.

By making the project outcomes available via The Embassy of Good Science, BEYOND will a) ensure long term availability of its result, b) allow stakeholders to engage with the materials by suggesting adaptations and sharing experiences and c) ensure dissemination of the outcomes towards a broader audience and established community of users.

4.3 Public consultation

BEYOND's public consultation platform was launched by WP2 in October 2023 to gather information from the general audience and other stakeholders (Fig. 5). The platform invites anyone interested to reflect on research ethics and research integrity and anonymously share their reflections with the BEYOND team. The public consultation survey has been approved by the University of Latvia Research Ethics Committee for Social Sciences and Humanities (approval no. 71-46/128).

The public consultation consists of a brief online questionnaire exploring research ethics and research integrity practices and research misconduct from the point of view of the general public and other stakeholders. The questionnaire is open until February 2024, and responses are sought from respondents in the European Economic Area (EU countries and Iceland, Liechtenstein and Norway), as well as Switzerland and United Kingdom. The public consultation is central to BEYOND for building a dialogue with the society and stakeholders on research ethics and research integrity.

The data collection is managed by the University of Latvia. The questionnaire is filled in anonymously, and answers to open-ended questions will be anonymised before data analysis. The data is stored in a secure server at the University of Latvia. Aggregated responses to this public consultation will inform project deliverables and scientific publications thereby allowing the perspectives of a broader audience to feed into the projects results.

Funded by the European Union

BEYOND
It takes the whole community to cultivate good research culture.

Beyond Bad Apples: Towards a Behavioural and Evidence-Based Approach to Promote Research Ethics and Research Integrity in Europe

Are you a citizen of EU, Iceland, Liechtenstein, Norway, Switzerland or the UK?

If so, it doesn't matter if you're a seasoned scientist, a student or someone who simply cares for good science...

...this is a call for you to participate in BEYOND Public Consultation!

Participate by completing the survey until 28th February 2024.

Read more about BEYOND and find the survey on the home page on <https://beyondbadapples.eu/> or scan the QR code to go to the survey directly:

We have put together an **anonymous online survey** that aims to explore the opinions on research ethics, integrity and research misconduct.

Yes, **you are our target audience!** You will be assigned a different set of questions based on your level of familiarity with research matters.

Information on Data Privacy and more will be presented to you at the beginning of the survey.

Fig. 5. Leaflet advertising BEYOND's public consultation survey (WP2)

4.4 Collaboration with other EU projects

Horizontal coordination with other EU-funded projects in the Horizon 2020 SwafS and in the Horizon Europe Widera programs enables cross-fertilization between projects for mutual benefit and co-creation.

Adjacent to the 2023 ENRIO Congress on Research Integrity Practice in Europe, a satellite session was organised by BEYOND on the 6th of September 2023 (Fig. 6). This session, which represented milestone 7.3 in the BEYOND project, operated as an extended Cross-SwafS forum. It was organised by Ofis in collaboration with ENRIO.

Fig. 6. Screenshot of the invitation to the satellite session

This session brought together approximately 45 experts, including of ENRIO members and representatives of 22 EU projects on research integrity and research ethics. . This event provided a space for cross-pollination of goals, methods, and results within projects in order to minimize the risk of duplicating efforts and optimise collaboration across various EU projects. Moreover the session provided space to discuss the new [European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity](#), and its value for and uptake within various EU projects. In the table below the project represented in the session are listed (Table 4).

Table 4. List of EU projects in the ENRIO 2023 pre-congress session

BEYOND
EnTIRE
ETHNA System
HYBRIDA
INTEGRITY
iRECS
iRISE
OSIRIS
Path2integrity

PATTERN
PERITIA
POIESIS
PREPARED
PRO-Ethics
ROSiE
SIENNA
SOPs4RI
TechEthos
TIER2
VERITY
VIRT²UE & The Embassy of Good Science
XR4HUMAN

The projects presented their aims, activities and outcomes by producing posters, available here:

<https://premc.org/enrio2023/conference-rooms/enrio-pre-congress-session-poster-area/>

In addition, four workshop were organized to discussed the following topics:

- 1) How to better foster collaboration between EU projects and ENRIO
- 2) How EU projects comply with the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity (ECoC)
- 3) How EU projects can supplement the ECoC
- 4) What are the main priorities for research integrity in Europe

The outcomes of the workshops will be summarised in a report by Ofis in c. March 2024. This report will provide insights for the European RI and RE community, via the networks of ENRIO, Ofis and the various stakeholders present at the pre-congress session.

Another similar event (not organised by BEYOND) is anticipated to take place in the 2024 WCRI.

4.5 Publications

In the first year of its activities, BEYOND project members have published the following academic publications:

- Rodrigues R. and Pizzolato D. Insights on the socio-economic impacts of research misconduct (submitted to Research Ethics – Special issue on Research Integrity and Research Misconduct. OA journal)
- Tammeleht, A., & Löfström, E. (2023). Learners' self-assessment as a measure to evaluate the effectiveness of research ethics and integrity training: Can we rely on self-reports?

- Ethics & Behavior. <https://doi.org/10.26529/cepsj.1564> (OA)
- Löffström, E. & Tammeleht, A. (to be published Nov 2023). A pedagogy for teaching research ethics and integrity in the social sciences: Case-based and collaborative learning. In G. Curtis (Ed.) *Academic Integrity in the Social Sciences. Perspectives on Pedagogy and Practice* (127-145). Springer. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-43292-7> (Field: Education)
 - Löffström, E. & Tammeleht, A. (2023). Understanding the Middle Position, and the relation of virtues and actions. In S. E. Eaton & R. Kumar (Eds.), *Lessons in Academic Integrity: Practical Ideas for Teaching, Learning, and Assessment* (pp. 36-39). University of Calgary. <https://dx.doi.org/10.11575/PRISM/42226>. (OA, Field: Education)
 - Löffström, E. & Tammeleht, A. (2023). Self-declaration of one's research and the multifaceted nature of goodness in research. In S. E. Eaton & R. Kumar (Eds.), *Lessons in Academic Integrity: Practical Ideas for Teaching, Learning, and Assessment* (pp. 31-35). University of Calgary. <https://dx.doi.org/10.11575/PRISM/42226>. (OA, Field: Education)
 - Löffström, E. & Tammeleht, A. (2023). Debate vs Dialogue and applying the discussion skills during the Dilemma Game. In S. E. Eaton & R. Kumar (Eds.), *Lessons in Academic Integrity: Practical Ideas for Teaching, Learning, and Assessment* (pp.40-44). University of Calgary. <https://dx.doi.org/10.11575/PRISM/42226>. (OA, Field: Education)

Open access principles

BEYOND follows the principles of responsible open science, as stipulated in the UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science and the ROSiE Responsible Open Science General Guidelines. Concretely, this means that BEYOND will utilize open science practices in communication, exploitation, and dissemination activities, and will do so responsibly.

BEYOND's publications will all be open access, and will as much as possible make its research products accessible in accordance with the FAIR and CARE principles.

5. Exploitation

BEYOND represents a concerted effort to address and mitigate research misconduct, while promoting the highest standards of research ethics and integrity. Our primary aim is to investigate the root causes of research misconduct, develop effective methodologies for measuring the impact of training on ethical behaviors, and design interventions that encourage good research practices. These objectives are underpinned (among others) by the creation of a best-practice manual, comprehensive guidelines, and a forward-looking roadmap, all aimed at bolstering the research ecosystem's commitment to ethical standards.

Our target audience is diverse, encompassing the broader research community, Research Performing and Funding Organizations (RPOs and RFOs), policymakers, Research Ethics and Research Integrity (RE/RI) committees and officers, and the general public. The success of our exploitation efforts will be gauged through a multi-faceted approach. This includes deriving insights from literature reviews and real-life cases of research misconduct, engaging in extensive public consultation, and producing detailed reports on intervention strategies and measurement methodologies. The development of practical tools, such as a best-practices manual and guidelines, along with the implementation of pilot-tested training materials, further

signifies our commitment to this cause. Our comprehensive dissemination and communication strategies are designed to ensure that the project's findings and resources are effectively shared and utilized across all relevant sectors and stakeholders.

5.1 Training Materials and Tools

Trainer guides will be developed within the project. A trainer guide is a document or resource that provides instructional guidance and support to trainers facilitating a training session. It serves as a roadmap for trainers, offering them step-by-step instructions, tips, and information on how to effectively deliver training sessions and achieve the desired learning outcomes. Similar trainer guides were created by [VIRT2UE on The Embassy of Good Science](#) and are currently being used in the ongoing VIRT2UE trainings. A similar template will be reused by BEYOND, building upon previous experiences and maximizing on previous projects results. The trainer guide will provide practical guidance on how to effectively teach RE/RI to different target groups, such as students, early career researchers, and experienced researchers, using a variety of methodologies.

Training materials will be developed based on insights coming from D6.1. WP6 will develop two sets of materials and tools: 1) training materials on responsible mentoring, supervision, and leadership for senior researchers and senior research managers and 2) training materials incorporating a gamification approach to refine and broaden a value-reflection game methodology that raises awareness for RE/RI, especially among students, early-career researchers.

5.2 Policy Briefs

BEYOND operates on a non-commercial basis, focusing primarily on producing training materials and policy options. The main goal of BEYOND'S two Policy Briefs is to suggest potential policies that can address identified issues in research environment that may hinder the implementation of research integrity policies. Additional assistance for stakeholders at the policy level involves providing practical guidelines, operational advice, and concise supplements to existing codes. These resources aim to support policy makers, and ethics committees and research integrity bodies in HEIs and RPOs.

Both Policy Briefs are specifically crafted for individual issues, using inclusive language. The topics are chosen in collaboration with policymakers through Stakeholder Advisory Board to ensure relevance. Before being made public, the briefs undergo discussions with key stakeholders to gather feedback and diverse perspectives. Once released, the policy briefs and options will be presented and distributed at significant policy events and through various networks.

BEYOND's first Policy Brief (D7.3) addressed the socio-economic consequences of RM, and it was targeted for the European Commission, national research integrity bodies, the European Network of Research Integrity Offices (ENRIO), and the European Network of Research Ethics and Research Integrity (ENERI).

5.3 Guidelines, Best Practice Manual, and Roadmap

BEYOND will co-create a case-based, context-sensitive, and practice-oriented best practice manual of effective measures for the various stakeholders to promote RE/RI and address RM. By best practices, we mean a technique or methodology that through experience and research has proven reliably to lead to the desired result.

To supplement existing standard operating procedures of RE/RI and RM, BEYOND will produce guidelines to facilitate the adoption of gained knowledge by researchers and RPOs.

Lastly, BEYOND will draft a RE/RI Roadmap to 2030 that outlines RE/RI goals but also challenges.

To develop these documents, we will utilize the steps to guideline development as expounded in WHO-commissioned articles. We will coordinate with WPs 1, 2, 3, 4, and 7 and the Stakeholder Advisory Board for the initial guideline, manual and roadmap scoping, which will be defined and redefined by stakeholder consultations in WP2; evidence mapping via literature review and the review of actual cases from WP1; evidence produced by WP3 on the interventions to address RM; inputs from Horizontal Coordination from WP7; the methodologies for the assessment of training effects from WP4; the review of existing guidelines and frameworks by SOPs4RI, TRUST, PRO-RES and PRO-Ethics; and the plotting of the complexity features as elaborated by Movsisyan and colleagues¹³. This will be followed by the formulation and reformulation of the guideline, manual, and roadmap questions. The following are examples of set of topics that will be formulated into questions based on the scope and intent of each of the three documents, and the questions reformulated based on the inputs of the WPs: institutional/environmental factors that lead to RM; individual factors that lead to RM; institutional responsibilities in the promotion of RE/RI; individual responsibilities of researchers in the promotion of RE/RI; institutional culture of researcher exploitation (including gender-based violence), taking into account the institutional impact on researchers' mental health and well-being, especially those employed in uncertain conditions; best practices in the reintegration of researchers after RM; effective and non-punitive behavioral approaches to address RM; responsible mentoring, supervision, and role modelling; and effective behavioral approaches to promote RE/RI. Next, the evidence gathered from WPs 1, 2, 3, 4, and 7 will be synthesized using a convergent synthesis design where both “qualitative and quantitative research is collected and analyzed. Adopting a parallel-results convergent synthesis design, the integration of results will happen after qualitative and quantitative results have been analyzed and presented separately by the different WPs. The relevant WPs will have qualitatized their quantitative results and assessed their evidence (using measures such as Q-SEA for the assessment of ethical analyses or other comparable and relevant assessment methods), allowing for such results to be ready for guideline development. Lastly, recommendations will be developed using the relevant sections of the WHO-INTEGRATE framework⁴⁶ to nuance the responses to the guideline, manual, and roadmap questions. The importance of the criteria and the eventual expression of evidence to recommendations will be weighed using Reflective Equilibrium. In cooperation with WPs 2 and 8, the documents will undergo public consultation processes and reviewed by the Stakeholder Advisory Board before being finalized.

6. Visual identity

The Finnish design company [Taikalehto](#) created the website and visual elements of the project.

The colour scheme consists of fresh shades of apple green, and the font selected is Open Sans. See Fig. 7 (here below) for reference.

Fig. 7 Fonts and colors used on BEYOND's materials.

It's the Orchard, Not the Apples (beyondbadapples.eu)